
Digitized Instructional Assessment (DIA) in Teaching Verb Tenses Among Underperforming Students: An Explanatory Sequential Design

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ABSTRACT: Digital tools play a pivotal role in creating an interactive learning environment. Hence, it is best to utilize digitized teaching to the students. This mixed-method employing explanatory sequential design used quasi-experimental design, particularly one- group pretest-post-test approach and phenomenology in the qualitative phase. This study aimed to determine the effectiveness of Digitized Instructional Assessment in teaching the tenses of verbs among the Grade 7 learners. Particularly it identified whether the pre-test and post-test result have a significant difference. It also described how the learners experienced DIA during classes. The intervention was employed among 20 grade 7 students who were identified using a purposive sampling technique. The result revealed that the level of pre-test is low while the post-test is high. Therefore, there is significant difference between the pre-test and post-test. This showed how effective the intervention was in learning the tenses of verbs in a digitized perspective. The themes formulated from their experiences of the students were interactive learning, convenient learning, and common challenges in learning. With these results, it is recommended that teachers may incorporate technology into the teaching and learning process, particularly when teaching grammar.

KEYWORDS: Digitized Instructional Assessment (DIA), *Explanatory sequential approach*, *Verb tenses*, *Grade 7 students*

I. INTRODUCTION

As a language of global scope, English facilitates communication in nearly every facet of human existence. However, learners struggle in learning grammar. The study showed that learners find it confusing to use simple present instead of present continuous for permanent situations which is caused by inappropriate teaching methodologies (Ali, S. et al., 2021). Moreover, learners demonstrated challenges in several areas of grammatical competence, including the adherence to subject-verb agreement, the correct employment of pronouns, and the accurate use of auxiliary verbs. These mistakes were associated with a lack of awareness of tense patterns and a lack of grammatical knowledge (Hadayani, 2019). Additionally, learners frequently struggle with subject-verb agreement, plural markers, tenses, and verb tense confusion when learning L2 grammatical norms, which may be impacted by their linguistic contexts (Dr. Muhammad Ahsan, 2020).

In Indonesia, issues were identified, difficulties in mastering specific English verb tenses, including the past perfect progressive, past perfect, and future perfect progressive, have been observed among Indonesian learners, attributed to factors such as aspect and tense application, first language interference, diminished confidence, and limited exposure. Conversely, conventional English tense instruction has been documented to pose challenges for learners, particularly in the application of the indefinite future and present progressive tenses. Also, traditional English teaching approaches have failed to keep students consistently engaged; this finding suggests that integrating tools can enhance the learning experience for English verb tenses (Listia, 2020; Sourav, 2021).

Furthermore, research conducted from the Philippines consequently documents the challenges encountered by Filipino learners in mastering verb tense acquisition. Indigenous learners struggled with English vocabulary, which likely affected their comprehension and usage of verb tenses (Leaño, 2019).

Moreover, traditional teaching approaches in the Philippines, especially in the teaching of tenses, have been proven to contribute to students' difficulties acquiring competence in both Filipino and English (Langga, et al., 2021). In addition, the study showed that students frequently struggle with the correct application of time markers in constructing sentences in the past and past perfect tense, as well as the irregular verb forms. Also, errors in verb conjugation and tense agreement are the result of the influence of the Filipino language structure on learning English tenses (Somoson, 2020).

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Moreover, in one of the schools in Bansalan Davao del Sur, an initial assessment of verb tense knowledge administered to 20 seventh-grade learners via a 20-question assessment, revealed significant challenges. Specifically, only one student achieved a score of 13, falling below the 75% passing threshold. Further, 5 learners scored 11, and 2 learners received a score of 6, the lowest recorded. These results strongly indicate a widespread difficulty with verb tenses among the tested learners.

It has been demonstrated that using technology in education, particularly when teaching verb tenses, improves student learning and engagement (Lumpkin, 2015). The research issue presents in various nations, specifically in the areas of education. Studies from international and national settings are present. Despite extensive review, this particular phenomenon has not been documented within the local setting, thereby necessitating the present study. Furthermore, there is no existing study in St. Mary's College of Bansalan utilizing the Explanatory Sequential mixed method approach to tenses of verbs, particularly the past tense and past perfect tense, where an intervention plan is provided through the use of Digitized Instructional Assessment. Also, this study will test the effectiveness of DIA in addressing the verb tenses difficulties of underperforming grade 7 learners. This research can help to inform evidence-based methods for targeted intervention and accelerate learning in this vital area. The study is also relevant as it provides educators with practical solutions for addressing verb tense issues and increasing language skills and academic confidence, thereby encouraging learners to succeed in their educational path. Moreover, this study is useful particularly in the teaching-learning process regarding tenses of verbs, particularly the past tense and past perfect tense; the computer-based game tool designed by the researchers can be used as instructional material for teaching vocabulary to the learners.

II. RESEARCH PROBLEM

The primary objective of this study was to determine the effectiveness of Digitized Instructional Assessment (DIA) in learning the tenses of verbs among the underperforming grade 7 students using quasi-experimental research particularly one-group pretest-posttest design. Specifically, sought to address the following:

1. What is the Pre-test and Posttest mean percentage of Grade 7 learners who are exposed to Digitized Instructional Assessment (DIA)?
2. Is there a significant difference between the Pre-test and Posttest mean percentage of Grade 7 learners who are exposed to Digitized Instructional Assessment (DIA)?
3. What are the experiences of Grade 7 learners in learning the tenses of verbs using Digitized Instructional Assessment (DIA)?

III. METHOD

Research Design

The researchers utilized a mixed-method approach using Explanatory Sequential design. An explanatory sequential design is a mixed methods research design in which the quantitative part of data collection and analysis follows the qualitative phase of data collection and analysis (Fetters, 2013). In the quantitative phase, it used a Quasi-experimental research approach, particularly one-group pretest-posttest design. While in the qualitative phase, phenomenology was used to determine the experiences of learners in learning tenses of verbs using Digitized Instructional Assessment (DIA). The core nature of human experiences and the meaning people attach to those experiences are explored in *phenomenological research design*. It aims to capture the fundamental structures and key elements of these experiences without imposing prior hypotheses or judgments.

Research Participant

The participants in this study are 20 Grade 7 Junior High School students from Bansalan Davao del Sur for the school year 2023-2024. These 20 selected students were the students who performed poorly during the preliminary assessment of the tenses of verbs for all Grade 7 students. Students who matched the following criteria were included: they were Grade 7 students from Bansalan Davao del Sur; these particular students belonged to those who had not passed the preliminary assessment. On the other hand, students who have passed the preliminary assessment about the tenses of verbs are excluded.

Research Instrument.

The tool for Lecture Method and Digitized Instructional Assessment (DIA) is a computer-based application tool and other interactive online application tools: socrative, quizziz, wheel of names, and picker wheel.

Furthermore, this computer-based application tool was inspired by the English Verb Smash: Grammar game application. This is a rank game type wherein there are two certain topics that they can choose from: past tense and past perfect tense. Each rank level in this game has certain levels that they need to achieve in order to proceed to the next level and to escalate their rank in the game until they reach the highest rank, which is advanced. Each rank has three levels (beginner, intermediate, and advanced). Rank 1 is the beginner, which consists of easy-level questions; rank 2 is the intermediate, which consists of moderate-level questions; and rank 3 is the advanced, which consists of difficult-level questions. Each level consists of 20 questions. Meanwhile, Socrative is an

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engagement app that provides games and other activities for students. It has ready-made interactive resources that can enhance the learner's learning and understanding of the concept and lesson.

Furthermore, we used standardized tests for pre-test and post-test. In order to gather all the necessary data, an in-depth interview for qualitative was utilized, and for quantitative we had thematic analysis. Moreover, before we made and used standardized test questions, a Table of Specifications was made and underwent validation.

Procedure

In order for the researchers to gather the necessary information, they had undergone specific procedure to ensure smooth transition. Likewise, the researchers implemented a 40-item preliminary test on the tenses of verbs for all Grade 7 students to avoid bias. The test allowed the researchers to identify 20 underperforming learners who failed the assessment.

The implementation of Digitized Instructional Assessment was covered for 10 days. During the first day, the researchers conducted an orientation and then administered a 40-item paper and pencil test that served as a pre-test. Upon completion of the test, they immediately checked and recorded the scores of the students. Within 10 days, they provided various interactive activities about past tense and past perfect tense. These activities were integrated with computer-based game tools and other interactive online application tools that served as instructional material in the teaching-learning process: Kahoot, Socrative, Quizziz, Wheel of Names, Picker Wheel.

On the tenth and last day of implementation, the researchers implemented a post-test, the same test that they took during their pre-test but with modifications. Upon retrieval of the said post-test, the researchers immediately checked and recorded the scores of the students. In the post-implementation stage, the researchers had an in-depth interview of the 20 participants. They gathered and compared the data from the pre-test and post-test results of the students.

Ethical Consideration

The proponents meticulously adhered to all applicable ethical standards throughout the research process particularly managing the population and the data. Participation in this study was entirely voluntary, with respondents afforded complete autonomy in their decision to contribute. Following a thorough presentation of the study's objectives and potential benefits, the respondents' uncoerced consent was meticulously obtained and strictly respected. In addition, all respondent-provided personal and private data, essential for this investigation, were processed with scrupulous diligence and remained subject to absolute confidentiality. Moreover, the researchers asked permission from the school. The researchers also sought consent from the school principal, adviser, and participants through an informed consent form. The informed consent form incorporated the study's purpose, procedural details, potential risks and benefits, anticipated participant and societal advantages, confidentiality protocols, participation and withdrawal, investigators' contact information, and rights of the research participants. Signing the informed consent was a requirement for participation in the study.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Presented in this section are the results of the gathered data from the research conducted and the analysis and interpretations of the data based on the statistical analysis and thematic analysis employed in the study.

Pre-test and Post-test mean percentage of the Grade 7 learners exposed to the Intervention

The first objective of this study is to determine the pre-test and post-test mean percentage of the grade 7 learners exposed to Digitized Instructional Assessment (DIA) for learning the tense of verbs. This was identified after the researcher conducted an intervention of the 20 underperforming who are exposed to DIA.

Table 1. Pre-test and Post-test mean percentage of the Grade 7 learners exposed to the Intervention Plan

<i>Particulars</i>	<i>Mean Percentage</i>	<i>Description</i>
pre-test	27.05%	Did Not Meet Expectations
post-test	76.25%	Fairly proficient

Table 1 shows the pre-test including the post-test mean percentage who have experienced the Digitalized Instructional Assessment (DIA). The data revealed that the pre-test had a mean percentage of 27.05%, and it was described as *did not meet expectations*, which means students reflect poor ability in identifying tenses of verbs. Data further implies that students find it difficult to answer the different competencies when it comes to simple past tense and past perfect tense of verbs. This means that learners cannot apply the specific rules of simple past tense of the verb when this is used in a sentence. Therefore, learners do not know that simple past tense is a specific action completed in the past. They also do not know that there are two forms of verbs, regular

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and irregular verbs, which made them confused about the correct use of simple past tense. This supports the study of Oktaviani (2020), which found that learners struggled with both regular and irregular verbs in the simple past tense.

On the other hand, learners also have an issue with past perfect tense when this is used in a given sentence. Particularly, the learners do not know how to identify that past perfect tense happens when there's another action happen prior to the fulfillment of a certain action. Also, learners do not know the formula of past perfect tense, which is had + past participle. This supports the study of Jejiza Mae Antiquiera Balaoro, M. (2024) which highlights that students frequently struggle with past perfect tense due to contextual issues. Therefore, during the pre-test, learners performed poorly in the tenses of verbs since they had not yet been exposed to DIA.

Furthermore, the post-test had a mean percentage of 76.25%, and it was described as *fairly satisfactory*, which means the students are fairly proficient in the tenses of verbs. This implies that during the post-test, learners were exposed to DIA, and this significantly resulted in an improvement of the performance in tenses of verbs, particularly in the past perfect tense. This is further supported by the study of Nurlaela & Nawir (2020), which indicates that the digital learning platform considerably enhances students' comprehension of English tenses. Also, Refat (2020) supported this that by using a tense learning aid helped performance on paper tests.

Significant difference between the Pre-test and Post-Test Mean percentages of Grade 7 learners who are Exposed to the Intervention Plan

The second objective of this study is to determine the significant difference in the Pre-test and Post-test mean percentages of Grade 7 learners who are exposed to Digitized Instructional Assessment (DIA) for Learning Tenses of Verbs.

Table 2. Significant difference between the Pre-test and Post-test Mean percentages of Grade 7 learners who are Exposed to the Intervention Plan

<i>Pair of Variables</i>	<i>r-value</i>	<i>Df</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
pre-test and post-test	.558	39	.000	Significant.

Table 2 shows the significant difference in the pre-test and post-test mean percentages. It showed the significant difference in the pre-test and post-test mean percentages, with an *r*-value of (.558) with *P*-value of .000. Since the *p*-value is lesser than 0.05 level of significance, this quantitative finding indicates that the difference which is significant between variables is evident. Thus, there is a rejection of the null hypothesis. This implies that the use of Digitized Instructional Assessment (DIA) has greatly improved the performance of the grade 7 learners during the post-test. Furthermore, this practically proved that technological integration can enhance the teaching and learning process which has a significant effect on the student motivation and performance.

Therefore, this proves that the use of digitized instructional materials is necessary in the teaching and learning process, particularly in teaching tenses of verbs. This further supported by the study of Hernández-Garcia et al., (2019), that the use of digitized software program helps students identify form errors and provide self-correction feedback, significantly improving their tense comprehension. It has been proven that the comprehension of tenses, has been demonstrated to be improved using digitized platform (CG) methods this also confirm in the study of Wijaya and Hidarto (2018). Also, it has been proven that the creation of application of digital resources, such as e-books that concentrate on past tenses, are legitimate and successful methods for teaching language in a variety of settings, including English education programs (Almunawaroh et al., 2021).

Experiences of Grade 7 Learners in Learning the Tenses of Verbs Using the Intervention Plan

The third aim of this study is to describe the experiences among the twenty underperforming Grade 7 Learners in Learning Tenses of Verbs using Digitized Instructional Assessment (DIA). This was determined after the intervention was given and were followed by in-depth interview. Four three themes emerged namely (1) *Technology- Driven*, (2) *Gamified Learning*, and (3) *Convenience and Efficacy*.

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Table 3: Experiences of Grade 7 Learners in Learning the Tenses of Verbs using the Intervention Plan

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Core Ideas</i>
Technology-driven	Learning and teaching process is engaging when it is incorporated with technology Learners are active and engaged in the teaching and learning process using technology Learners were exposed to varied online application tools which made the learners more engaged
Gamified Learning	Learners learn easier when learning activities are gamified Learning became fun and exciting using games Learners were able to know how use and experience various gamified learning tools that enhances their learning
Convenience and Efficiency	Learners find digital assessment less time-consuming than paper and pencil assessment Learners were able to finish faster upon answering the assessment. Learners can answer multiple assessments in short amount of time

When asked about the experiences, students claim that the use of DIA provides them with interactive learning. Moreover, this interactive learning allows them to use technology in the teaching and learning process which allow them to engage in a more meaningful learning. Furthermore, this provides them with active and engaging learning experiences, as they were exposed to varied online application tools which made them more engaged and participative in the class. It also made learning fun, exciting and easier through hands-on experience of the digitized tools that enhances their learning. Moreover, Technological integration enables them to be active and attentive in class. This drives them with strong engagement and motivation to learn. Also, their eagerness to learn increases which made them less feel boredom.

In line with this, digital integration and innovative teaching methodologies can be more effective than traditional methods (Ancheta, Jeffrey Rosario, 2022). Also, Teopilus et al., (2019) demonstrated that digitized instructions significantly enhanced learners understanding of English verb tenses by minimizing explanations and enabling visual representation of actions. Moore-Stroble et al., (2022) found that digitized learning can be effective tools for teaching verb tenses. Based on the result students who used a mobile-based learning strategy showed improved academic performance in understanding and applying verb tenses. This is further supported by the study of Indra et al., (2023) which highlights that students adhere to technology-based instruction because it is efficient with regard to time, easy to use, and interesting.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the data gathered of the study, the following conclusions were formulated:

The data showed that the pre-test had mean percentage of 27.05% and it described as *did not meet expectations* which means students reflect poor ability in identifying tenses of verbs. Whereas, the post-test had a mean percentage of 76.25% and it described as *fairly satisfactory* which means the students are fairly proficient in the tenses of verbs who are now exposed to Digitized Instructional Assessment (DIA). Moreover, the *r-value* showed that there is a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test. The use Digitized Instructional Assessment (DIA) has greatly improved the learners’ performance in learning tenses of verbs. In this quantitative finding indicates that significant difference between variables is evident. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. In the qualitative part the data revealed that DIA allowed learners’ experience a gamified learning which is efficient and convenient for learning.

VI. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the conclusions, the recommendations were put forward for those concerns:

To the administration, it is now timely to adapt Digitized Instructional Assessment (DIA) because it is interactive, engaging, and dynamic since it can cater the different interests and learning styles and needs of the learners. Also, may they avail premium accounts, conduct training and seminar that leads to professional development opportunities for teachers to enhance their abilities in using technology and delivering differentiated and digitized instructions.

To the teachers, may they attend training and seminar to enhance and develop their teaching pedagogy. Additionally, may they focus on teaching the different form of verbs particularly the regular and irregular verbs in order for the learners to effectively use and identify the correct tenses in a sentence. Also, teachers may teach the learners the techniques on how to use and easily identify simple past and past perfect tense in a sentence. Furthermore, teachers may shift from traditional to digitized instructions and materials to have an engaging classroom environment. May they employ DIA on the teaching and learning process because this significantly show its effectiveness on teaching tenses.

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To the learners, they need to be clarified on the issues identifying the correct form and usage of tenses of verbs. Moreover, they need to learn first the regular and irregular verbs to effectively use and identify simple past and past perfect tense. Also, may they explore different online application tools: Grammarly, Verb2Verb, Tense Buster, Verb Conjugation, Tenses, English Grammar in Use, Duolingo, Merriam Webster, WordHippo, Grammar Bytes, and more which they can use to practice with in enhancing their English skills by themselves.

To the future researchers, may they still explore and use DIA on their study to confirm that the result of the study is valid for reliability purposes. Furthermore, may they design a learning application tools wherein it does not just focus on one topic. Furthermore, may they design more interactive digitized learning tools that is available for online and offline usage.

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